

The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia

Milka Pasulu¹, Andi Irfan², Pahmi³, Andi Alim⁴, Lenny Thalib⁵

^{1,2,5} Program Study of Management, College of Management Science-Indonesian Education Institute

³Program Study of Management, Faculty of Business Economics and Humanities, University of Education Muhammadiyah, Sorong

⁴Program Study of Public Health, University of Pejuang Republic Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The phenomenon related to the performance of employees at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency is that work is still not running optimally. This can be seen in terms of quality, there are still many employees who do not have the ability in their field of work. Based on this, this study aims to see the effect of job satisfaction and work motivation on employee performance through work discipline. The research method was used with a quantitative approach. The research population was 118 people while the samples taken were 100 people. The data collection method used in this study was the use of personally administered questionnaires. The results of the study found that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work discipline, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work discipline has a positive effect on performance employees, job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance through work discipline, work motivation has a positive effect on employee performance through work discipline. good and high job satisfaction will have an impact on increasing work discipline. High and good job satisfaction that is owned by each employee will be able to encourage employees to carry out their duties properly. Besides that, an employee's work motivation can have a real influence in improving the work discipline of other employees, so that employee motivation improves employee performance. In addition, good job satisfaction and work motivation will affect employee performance. This indicates that good work discipline can improve employee performance in carrying out their duties.

KEYWORDS: Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation, Employee Performance, Work Discipline

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important asset in an organization or agency because human resources are the main key that determines the success of an organization or agency in achieving its goals effectively and efficiently. Resources owned by organizations or agencies such as capital, methods and machines will not provide optimum results if they are not supported by human resources or employees who have optimum performance. Performance is the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as standard work results, targets or goals or criteria that have been determined in advance and have been mutually agreed upon (Rivai & Sagala, 2014). To improve employee performance so that the expectations and goals of the organization or agency can be achieved. Thus, organizations or agencies must pay attention to the factors that can affect the performance of these employees. Job satisfaction is a very important factor to get optimal work results. The reason for the assessment is to increase the level of job satisfaction of employees by giving recognition of their work (Hasibuan, 2016). Assessment of

employee job satisfaction will be understood through individual attitudes towards the work performed, the more aspects of the work that are by individual wishes, the higher the level of satisfaction felt. With job satisfaction obtained, it is expected that high employee performance can be achieved by employees. The above concept is in line with research conducted by Ibrahim (2012), based on the results of his research showing that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. According to Hasibuan (2016), job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that expresses pleasure and work. Work motivation can also affect employee performance. Motivation is a desire that arises in employees that creates enthusiasm or encouragement to work optimally to achieve goals. Motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates enthusiasm for one's work so that employees want to work optimally. With motivation, employees will be encouraged to do as much as possible in carrying out their duties.

Work discipline is a factor that can affect employee performance. Hasibuan (2016), says that many indicators affect the level of discipline of a person in an organization, one of which is remuneration or welfare salary which influences

employee discipline because remuneration will give employees satisfaction and love for their workplace. If the employee's love for work is higher, the discipline will be better. The above concept is in line with research conducted by Ilahi et al. (2017). In addition to job satisfaction factors that affect work discipline, work motivation factors also affect work discipline. Hasibuan (2016), says that among the goals of work motivation are creating a good working atmosphere and relationship, increasing a sense of responsibility for one's duties, and being able to increase one's discipline at work. The above concept is in line with research conducted by Pratama & Nurbudiawati (2016), where the results of their research show that work motivation influences work discipline. Work motivation is a condition or energy that drives employees who are directed or directed to achieve organizational goals. The positive mental attitude of employees towards work situations strengthens their work motivation to achieve maximum performance.

In addition to the factors of job satisfaction and work motivation that affect work discipline and employee performance in the explanation above, work discipline also affects employee performance. Wibowo (2016) and Hasibuan (2016), state that the higher the achievement motivation and work discipline, the employee's performance will also increase. According to (Sedarmayanti, 2011) one of the factors that influence performance is Mental Attitude (work motivation, work discipline, work ethics). The mental attitude possessed by an employee will influence his performance. Work discipline is one of the factors that can reflect the performance produced by employees. The above concept is in line with research conducted by Nathalia (2016), the results of her research show that work discipline has a significant influence on employee performance.

The object of research at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, as for the problems that exist at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, shows that employee job satisfaction is still low. This can be seen from some employees who feel that the task given to them is a boring routine so that the work/task given is neglected. Jobs that are always the same in an organization or agency make employees feel bored, they also like to complain about doing their work because they say they are bored and don't understand their work, some employees look worried, anxious, and feel uncomfortable getting the job done. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything that is encountered in the work environment. Each employee has a different level of satisfaction according to the values that apply to him. The more aspects of work that are by the wishes and aspects of the individual, the there is a tendency for the higher the level of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can influence the level of turnover and absenteeism on the physical and mental health of employees and the level of inactivity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Job Satisfaction

Porter and Lawler in Bavendam (2000), explain that job satisfaction is a unidimensional building, where a person has general satisfaction or dissatisfaction with his job. A positive attitude towards work conceptually can be expressed as job satisfaction and a negative attitude towards work equals dissatisfaction. Meanwhile, according to Usman (2013), job satisfaction, in general, is an attitude towards work that is based on the evaluation of different aspects for workers. A person's attitude toward the job describes pleasant or unpleasant experiences at work and expectations about future experiences.

Blum in Anoraga & Suyati (2015), states that job satisfaction is a general attitude which is the result of several specific characteristics of work factors, adjustment, and individual social relations outside of work. This is a subjective condition of a person's state of being happy or unhappy as a result of the urge or needs that exists in him and is associated with the perceived reality. Job satisfaction is closely related to what employees expect from their work by the perceived needs. Job satisfaction will be fulfilled if everyone can produce interesting work, is satisfied with the work challenges faced, gives an appreciation for the achievements produced, is satisfied with receiving awards and is satisfied with carrying out work responsibilities (Herzberg in Keban, 2007).

According to Kreitner & Kinicki (2014), job satisfaction is an effectiveness or emotional response to various aspects of work. Newstrom & Davis (2002), describe job satisfaction as a set of employee feelings about whether or not their job is enjoyable. According to Robbins et al. (2018), job satisfaction is a general attitude toward one's work that shows the difference between the amount of rewards workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive. Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that pleases and loves his job. This attitude is reflected in work morale, discipline and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed at work, outside work, and a combination of inside and outside of work (Hasibuan, 2016). Handoko (2016), suggests that job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state with which employees perceive their work. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work.

From several opinions formulated by experts regarding the notion of job satisfaction, it can be formulated that job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behaviour towards their work through an assessment of one's work as a sense of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of the work. Whereas in this study, job satisfaction is defined as a positive attitude from employees including feelings and behaviour towards their work through the assessment of one job as a sense of respect in achieving one of the important values of work.

2.2. Work Motivation

According to Vroom in Purwanto (2007), work motivation refers to a process of influencing individual choices of the various forms of activity desired. According to Uno (2023), work is 1) a basic activity and is made an essential part of human life, 2) work gives status, and binds a person to other individuals and society, 3) in general women or men like work, 4) moral many workers and employees do not have a direct relationship with the physical or material conditions of work, 5) work incentives take many forms, including money.

Work motivation is the encouragement and direction of behaviour, through incentives, attention and praise, managers can motivate people to work harder and better (Moekijat, 2010). A similar opinion was also expressed by Terry & Rue (2021), that work motivation is a person's effort to be able to complete work with enthusiasm because they want to do it. Work motivation is an impetus for a series of processes of human behaviour in achieving goals (Wibowo, 2016).

Work motivation is a desire within a person that causes that person to act (Mathis et al., 2019). Usually, people act for a reason to achieve goals. Understanding work motivation is very important because performance, reactions to compensation and other human resource issues are influenced and affect work motivation. What is meant by work motivation is the origin of the word motive, namely a will or desire that arises in a person that causes that person to act (Robert in Moenir, 1987). Huitt (2001), says work motivation is an internal condition or status (sometimes interpreted as a need, desire, or desire) that directs a person's behaviour to actively act to achieve a goal.

2.3. Work Discipline

According to Moekijat (2010), discipline is the ability to control oneself that is regulated. According to Markum (2016), discipline is an attitude of willingness and willingness of a person to understand and obey the norms of regulations that apply around him. Nitisemito (2018), states that work discipline is an attitude, behaviour and actions that are by organizational regulations, both written and unwritten. According to Sastrohadiwiryo & Hadaningsih Syuhada (2019), work discipline is an attitude of respecting, appreciating, obeying and obeying the applicable regulations both written and unwritten and being able to carry them out and not evading sanctions if he violates his duties and authorities. that was given to him.

Gie (2009), argues, discipline is a condition that can be said to be orderly where people who are members of an organization are happy to obey the rules. According to Wursanto (2009), work discipline is an orderly and regular way and lifestyle that is affected by self-control as an appearance of awareness and belief, identity and purpose as well as self-appearance of certain appreciations and values that have been entrenched inside.

According to Handoko (2016), discipline is a management activity to carry out organizational standards. There are two types of disciplinary activities, namely preventive and corrective. In the implementation of discipline, to obtain the expected results, the leader in his business needs to use certain guidelines as the basis for implementation. Siagian (2016), specifically provides the following understanding of work discipline, namely work discipline is an attitude of respect, respect, obedience and obedience to all applicable regulations, both written and unwritten and able to carry out and not evade accepting sanctions if he violates the duties and authority given to him.

2.4. Employee Performance

Performance (job performance) is a record of results or outputs (outcomes) resulting from a certain job function or certain activities in a certain period (Gomes, 2016). According to Mangkunegara (2016), performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by someone in carrying out their duties by the responsibilities given to them efficiently and effectively with full loyalty. According to Prawirosentono (2014), performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, by their respective authorities and responsibilities, to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and by with morals and ethics.

According to Hasibuan (2016), performance is a work result that is achieved by someone in carrying out their duties based on skill, effort and opportunity. Based on the explanation above, performance is a result achieved by someone in carrying out tasks based on skills, experience and sincerity as well as time according to predetermined standards and criteria.

Performance According to Gomes (2016), employee performance as an expression such as output, efficiency and effectiveness is often associated with productivity. Performance according to Simamora (2017), is to achieve that the organization functions effectively and by organizational goals, the organization must have good employee performance by carrying out its duties in a reliable manner. According to Mangkunegara (2016), performance (work achievement) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties by the responsibilities given to him. Performance according to Mathis et al. (2019), is what employees do or do not do.

According to Simamora (2017), the description of performance involves three important components, namely goals that will provide direction and influence how work behaviour should be expected by the organization for each personnel. The second is the measurement, needed to find out whether personnel has achieved the expected performance, for this reason, quantitative and qualitative performance standards for each personal task and position play an important role. Third, regular performance appraisal, which is linked to the process of achieving the performance goals of each personnel.

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

This action will make personnel always be goal-oriented and work behaviour by and in the direction of the goals to be achieved.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research approach is quantitative. Quantitative research approaches are methods for testing certain theories by examining the relationships between variables. This research was conducted at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency. The research subjects that will be used as populations are employees at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency with a total research population of 118 people, who will provide data and information about job satisfaction, work motivation, work discipline and employee performance. In this study, the employees at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency with a total sample of 100 people consisting of gender characteristics, namely 54 men and 46 women, will provide data and information about job satisfaction, work motivation, work discipline and employee performance (Cooper & Emory, 2006; Sugiyono, 2019; Bougie & Sekaran, 2019).

Data collection is carried out to obtain information needed in achieving research objectives. The data collection method that will be used in this study is to use personally administered questionnaires. Data was collected using a closed questionnaire (questionnaire), using a Likert scale. Data collection by observation was carried out at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency. Data was obtained directly with employees as respondents, in interviews asking questions which are statements of existing variables.

3.1. Data analysis technique

Test the instrument using the validity and reliability of the instrument. The reliability test is a tool to measure a questionnaire that has indicators of variables or constructs. Reliability and validity tests can be carried out using the SPSS program (Mas’ud, 2004; Priyatno, 2008; Ghozali, 2021). Then to obtain the results of the interpretation of the respondent's responses to the research variables, a scoring analysis was carried out for each variable (Sugiyono, 2019). Path analysis is used to analyze the pattern of relationships between variables

to know the direct and indirect effects of a set of independent (exogenous) variables on the dependent (endogenous) variable. In path analysis, before the researcher analyzes a study, the researcher first creates a path diagram that is used to present problems in the form of pictures and determines structural equations that express the relationships between variables in the path diagram (Noor, 2015; Ghozali, 2021).

Test the instrument using the validity and reliability of the instrument. The reliability test is a tool to measure a questionnaire that has indicators of variables or constructs. Reliability and validity tests can be carried out using the SPSS program (Mas’ud, 2004; Priyatno, 2008; Ghozali, 2021). Then to obtain the results of the interpretation of the respondent's responses to the research variables, a scoring analysis was carried out for each variable (Sugiyono, 2019). Path analysis is used to analyze the pattern of relationships between variables to know the direct and indirect effects of a set of independent (exogenous) variables on the dependent (endogenous) variable. In path analysis, before the researcher analyzes a study, the researcher first creates a path diagram that is used to present problems in the form of pictures and determines structural equations that express the relationships between variables in the path diagram (Noor, 2015; Ghozali, 2021).

3.2. Validity test

Testing the validity of the instrument is calculating the correlation coefficient between item scores and the total score at a significance level of 95% or $\alpha = 0.05$ (Santoso, 2020). The validity test with this method was carried out by correlating the answer scores obtained for each question item with the total score of all question items. Correlation results must be significant based on statistical measures. A high correlation coefficient indicates the suitability between the item function and the measurement function as a whole or in other words the instrument is valid. Validity is performed using the product-moment correlation coefficient if the value of r count ≥ 0.195 (r table). To find out the validity test on the variables Job Satisfaction (X1), Work Motivation (X2), Work Discipline (Y1) and Employee Performance (Y2) can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Validity Test Results of Job Satisfaction (X1), Work Motivation (X2), Work Discipline (Y1) and Employee Performance (Y2)

Research variable	R count	R table	Sig	Information
Job Satisfaction (X1)				
X1.1	0.791	0.195	0.000	Valid
X1.2	0.799	0.195	0.000	Valid
X1.3	0.777	0.195	0.000	Valid
X1.4	0.784	0.195	0.000	Valid
X1.5	0.809	0.195	0.000	Valid
Work Motivation (X2)				
X2.1	0.861	0.195	0.000	Valid
X2.2	0.851	0.195	0.000	Valid

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

X2.3	0.797	0.195	0.000	Valid
X2.4	0.885	0.195	0.000	Valid
X2.5	0.845	0.195	0.000	Valid
Work Discipline (Y1)				
Y11	0.700	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y12	0.841	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y13	0.748	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y14	0.891	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y15	0.891	0.195	0.000	Valid
Employee Performance (Y2)				
Y21	0.765	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y22	0.808	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y23	0.682	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y24	0.597	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y25	0.650	0.195	0.000	Valid
Y26	0.810	0.195	0.000	Valid

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

3.3. Reliability Test

Testing the reliability or reliability of the instrument is a test of the level of consistency of the instrument itself. A good instrument must be consistent with the items being measured. The reliability of the instruments in the research conducted will be analyzed using the Cronbach's Alpha technique with the help of the SPSS 25 program. The cut of point accepted for the

Cronbach's Alpha level is ≥ 0.60 , although this is not an absolute standard (Bougie & Sekaran, 2019). But this is a general standard used in research. The instrument is considered to have an acceptable level of reliability if the measured reliability coefficient is ≥ 0.60 . The results of the reliability test of each variable used in this study can be seen in table 2 below

Table 2. Research Questionnaire Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Standards	Information
1.	Job Satisfaction (X1)	0.845	0.60	Reliabel
2	Work Motivation (X2)	0.900	0.60	Reliabel
3.	Work Discipline (Y1)	0.863	0.60	Reliabel
4	Employee performance (Y2)	0.779	0.60	Reliabel

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

4. RESULTS

4.1 Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics of respondents based on gender, age, education, and years of service are described in the following table:

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics of Gender, Age, Education, and Years of Service

Respondent Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Man	54	54.0
Woman	46	46.0
Age (Years)		
20-30	47	47.0
31-40	41	41.0
41-50	10	10.0
>50	2	2.0
Education		
Senior High School	25	25.0
3-Year Diploma	11	11.0
Bachelor Degree	55	55.0
Masters	9	9.0

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

Service Period (Year)		
1-5	26	26.0
6-10	48	48.0
11-15	16	16.0
16-20	8	8.0
>20	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

4.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Variables Job Satisfaction (X1), Work Motivation (X2), Work Discipline (Y1), and Employee Performance (Y2)

The object analysis in this study is the effect of job satisfaction and work motivation on employee performance through work discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency. Variables of job satisfaction, work motivation and work

discipline in the study were measured through 5 statement items while for employee performance variable (Y2) in the study were measured through 6 statement items which presented the indicators of these variables. For an overview obtained from the respondents' assessment of the variables of job satisfaction, work motivation, work discipline and employee performance (Y2) can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. Frequency/Percentage of Variable Indicators Job Satisfaction Job Satisfaction (X1), Work Motivation (X2), Work Discipline (Y1), and Employee Performance (Y2)

Indicator	Means	Category
Job Satisfaction (X1)		
Skills in Work (X11)	4.34	Very High
Fulfillment of Salary (X12)	4.17	Very High
Supervision from superiors (X13)	4.35	Very High
Career Advancement Opportunity (X14)	4.56	Very High
Good relationship among colleagues and superiors (X15)	4.16	Very High
Mean Job Satisfaction	4.31	Very High
Work Motivation (X2)		
Proposed ideas or arguments to instill in colleagues (X21)	4.35	Very High
Routine supervision carried out by superiors on subordinates (X22)	4.57	Very High
Dependence among fellow employees or colleagues in solving problems (X23)	4.40	Very High
Efforts to increase self-potential through education or training (X24)	4.45	Very High
Openness among fellow employees in the work environment (X25)	4.60	Very High
Mean Work Motivation	4.47	Very High
Work Discipline (Y1)		
Arrive at the office on time (Y11)	4.34	Very High
Work according to established work standards (Y12)	4.35	Very High
Work according to established procedures (Y13)	4.43	Very High
Work according to established procedures (Y13)	4.57	Very High
Be polite while in the office (Y15)	4.57	Very High
Mean Work Discipline	4.45	Very High
Employee performance (Y2)		
The assignments given are in accordance with the quality of work (Y21)	4.35	Very High
The number of activities assigned according to the target achieved (Y22)	4.56	Very High
High work commitment to work and responsible for his office (Y23)	4.57	Very High
Ability to do work (Y24)	4.31	Very High
Attendance will come to work every day and according to working hours (Y25)	4.10	Very High
Ability to cooperate among colleagues (Y6)	4.47	Very High
Mean Employee Performance	4.39	Very High

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

4.3 Research Analysis

To see the results of research on the effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline, an analytical method called path analysis is used. The model in the path analysis is divided into two substructures, the following is the test for each substructure:

4.3.1 Substructural Path Analysis I

To see the effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Work Discipline, substructure path analysis is

used. Based on the results of data processing with the help of the SPSS 25.0 program, a summary of the empirical results of the research is shown as follows: Analysis of Regression Coefficient of Substructure 1

a. Partial (Individual) Testing of Sub-structures 1

To determine the partial (individual) effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Work Discipline is presented in Table 5 as follows

Table 5. Results of Sub-structure Path Analysis 1

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.914	1.123		2.595	.011		
	Job satisfaction	.315	.062	.340	5.041	.000	.547	1.828
	Work motivation	.561	.063	.604	8.948	.000	.547	1.828

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

Based on table 5 above, it can be seen that the significance value for the variable Job Satisfaction on Work Discipline is 0.000 and the significance value for the variable Work Motivation on Work Discipline is 0.000, because a significance value of less than 0.05 means that the variable Job

Satisfaction (X1) and Work Motivation (X2) has a positive and significant effect on work discipline (Y1).

b. Testing the Coefficient of Determination (R Square) Substructure 1

The price of the correlation of determination or R square as described in Table 6. Below.

Table 6. Substructure Determination Test Results 1

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.871 ^a	.758	.753	1.456

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

Based on the calculation results, the correlation coefficient price is obtained with an R square value of 0.758. The price of the coefficient of determination (R²) shows that the contribution of the determination of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation to Work Discipline is 75.8%. While the remaining 24.2% is the influence of other factors that are not included in this model. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the path

coefficient for other variables outside the study is $(pY_{e1}) = \sqrt{1-R^2} = \sqrt{1-0.758} = 0.491$

Based on the results of the above tests, a path diagram for sub-structure 1 is obtained which can be described as follows:

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

Figure 1. Sub-structure Path Diagram 1

Thus the structural equation for sub-structure 1 can be obtained, namely: $Y_1 = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_1$. So, $Y_1 = 2.914 + 0.340 X_1 + 0.604 X_2 + 0.491$. Based on the structural equation of sub-structure 1, it can be interpreted that: first, the value of the Beta coefficient (Standardized Coefficient Beta column) the effect of representative Job Satisfaction on Work Discipline ($X_1 \rightarrow Y_1$) is 0.340

which indicates that if the value of Job Satisfaction increases by 1 point, then the value Work Discipline will increase by 0.340; and secondly, the Beta coefficient value (Standardized Coefficient Beta column) for the effect of

representative Work Motivation on Work Discipline ($X_2 \rightarrow Y_1$) is 0.604 which indicates that if the Work Motivation value increases by 1, then the Work Discipline value will increase by 0.604.

4.3.2 Substructural Path Analysis II

To see the effect of Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on employee performance, substructure path analysis is used. Based on the results of data processing with the help of the SPSS 25.0 program, a summary of the empirical research results can be seen as follows:

a. Partial (Individual) Testing of Sub-structures 2

Determine the partial (individual) Effect of Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on employee performance is presented in Table 7 as follows:

Table 7. Results of Sub-structure Path Analysis 2

Coefficients ^a								
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.124	1.202		1.767	.080		
	Job satisfaction	.640	.073	.579	8.809	.000	.433	2.307
	Work motivation	.177	.088	.159	2.013	.040	.300	3.337
	Work Discipline	.291	.105	.244	2.769	.007	.242	4.132

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 2021

Based on Table 7 above, it can be seen that the significance value for the Job Satisfaction variable on employee performance is 0.000, the significance value for the Work Motivation variable on employee performance is 0.040 and the significance value for the Work Discipline variable on employee performance is 0.007 because the significance value is less than 0.05 means that the variables Job Satisfaction (X1),

Work Motivation (X2) and Work Discipline (Y1) have a positive and significant influence on employee performance (Y2).

b. Testing the Coefficient of Determination (R Square) Substructure 2

The price of the correlation of determination or R square is described in Table 8 below:

Table 8. Substructure Determination Test Results 2

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.906 ^a	.820	.814	1.507

Source: Primary data processed (SPSS 25) 202

Based on the calculation results, the correlation coefficient price is obtained with an R square value of 0.820. The price coefficient of determination (R²) indicates that the contribution of the determination of Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation and Work Discipline to Employee Performance is 82.0%. While the remaining 18.0% is the influence of other factors that are not

included in this model. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the path coefficient for other variables outside the study is $(pYe_2) = \sqrt{1 - R^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0.820} = 0.424$.

Based on the results of the above tests, a path diagram for sub-structure 2 is obtained which can be described as follows:

Figure 2. Sub-structure Path Diagram 2

Thus the structural equation for sub-structure 2 can be obtained, namely $Y_2 = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Y_1 + e_2$. So, $Y_2 = 2.124 + 0.579 X_1 + 0.159 X_2 + 0.244 Y_1 + 0.424$. Based on the structural equation of sub-structure 2, it can be interpreted that: first, the value of the Beta coefficient (Standardized Coefficient Beta column) the effect of representative Job Satisfaction on employee performance ($X_1 \rightarrow Y_2$) is 0.579 which indicates that if the value of Job Satisfaction increases by 1 point, then employee performance value will increase by 0.579; second, the value of the Beta coefficient (Standardized Coefficient Beta) the effect of representative Work Motivation on employee performance

($X_2 \rightarrow Y_2$) is 0.159 which indicates that if the Work Motivation value increases by 1, then the employee performance value will increase by 0.159; and third, the Beta coefficient value (Standardized Coefficient Beta column) the effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance ($Y_1 \rightarrow Y_2$) is 0.244 which indicates that if the Work Discipline value increases by 1, then the Employee Performance value will increase by 0.244

4.3.3 Hypothesis test Thus the overall causal influence of the variables Job Satisfaction (X1) and Work Motivation (X2) on employee performance (Y2) through Work Discipline can be described in the structural model as follows:

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

Figure 3. Overall Path Diagram of Research Structure

Based on figure 3, the overall path diagram of the research structure from the existing causality relationships, it can be seen the direct, indirect and total effects. Following are

the overall results of the research structure which are displayed in the following table 9

Table 9. Summary of Influence Results

Variabel	Variabel	Koefisien jalur	Standardized Coefficients	Sig.	Std. Error
Prosperity (X1)	Work Discipline (Y1)	X1 → Y1	0.340	0.000	0.062
Work Motivation (X2)		X2 → Y1	0.604	0.000	0.063
Prosperity (X1)	Employee performance (Y2)	X1 → Y2	0.579	0.000	0.073
Work Motivation (X2)		X2 → Y2	0.159	0.040	0.088
Work Discipline (Y1)		Y1 → Y2	0.244	0.007	0.105
Job Satisfaction(X1)		X1 → Y1 → Y2	0.661		
Work Motivation (X2)		X2 → Y1 → Y2	0.306		
Total effect (X1) → (Y2)		X1 → Y2	0.579 + 0.661 = 1.240		
Total effect (X2) → (Y2)		X2 → Y2	0.159 + 0.306 = 0.465		
e1			0.491		
e2			0.424		

Source: Computational Results

5. DISCUSSION

Based on the research results that have been presented in the previous chapter, the following research results will be discussed:

5.1. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Work Discipline

The regression coefficient on the Job Satisfaction variable influences Work Discipline. Hasibuan (2016), says that many indicators affect the level of discipline of a person in an organization, one of which is remuneration or welfare salary

which influences employee discipline because remuneration will give employees satisfaction and love for their workplace. If the employee's love for work is higher, the discipline will be better. The conceptual framework regarding the effect of job satisfaction on work discipline is also supported by research conducted by Ilahi et al. (2017), research findings show that job satisfaction has a significant and positive influence on work discipline.

5.2. Effect of Work Motivation on Work Discipline

The regression coefficient on the variable Work Motivation influences Work Discipline. Hasibuan (2016), says that among the goals of work motivation are creating a good working atmosphere and relationship, increasing a sense of responsibility towards one's duties, and being able to increase one's discipline at work. The conceptual framework regarding the influence of work motivation on work discipline is also supported by research conducted by Pratama & Nurbudiawati (2016), the findings of the research show that work motivation influences work discipline

5.3. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The regression coefficient on the Job Satisfaction variable affects employee performance. Performance appraisal is one of the methods that can be used by organizations to find out and assess how much employee satisfaction is with their work and their work environment. The reason for the assessment is to increase the level of job satisfaction of employees by giving recognition of their work (Hasibuan, 2016). Assessment of employee job satisfaction will be understood through individual attitudes towards the work performed, the more aspects of the work that are by individual wishes, the higher the level of satisfaction felt. With job satisfaction obtained, it is expected that high employee performance can be achieved by employees. The conceptual framework regarding the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance is also supported by research conducted by Ibrahim (2012), the findings of the study show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance.

5.4. Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

The regression coefficient on the variable Work Motivation influences employee performance. According to Siagian (2016), work motivation is the driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to mobilize abilities in the form of expertise or skills of personnel and time to carry out various activities for which they are responsible and fulfil their obligations, to achieve organizational goals and objectives. predetermined. According to Gomes (2016), performance is a function of work motivation and ability. Ability is inherent in a person and is innate and manifested in his actions at work, while work motivation is a very important aspect to drive one's creativity and ability to do a job, and always be enthusiastic in carrying out the work. The conceptual framework regarding the effect of work motivation on employee performance is also supported by research conducted by Ramadhani & Dwihartanti (2016), the findings of the study show that there is a positive influence between work motivation on employee performance.

5.5. Effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance

The regression coefficient on the Work Discipline variable influences employee performance. Wibowo (2016)

and Hasibuan (2016), state that the higher the achievement motivation and work discipline, the employee's performance will also increase. According to Sedarmayanti (2011), one of the factors that influence performance is Mental Attitude (work motivation, work discipline, and work ethics). The mental attitude possessed by an employee will influence his performance. Work discipline is one of the factors that can reflect the performance produced by employees. The conceptual framework regarding the influence of work discipline on employee performance is also supported by research conducted by Nathalia (2016), the findings of the study show that work discipline has a significant influence on employee performance.

5.6. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance through Work Discipline

Thus, hypothesis 6 which states that Job Satisfaction has a positive effect through Work Discipline on employee performance at the Regional Secretariat for the General Section of East Luwu Regency, is accepted. Performance Appraisal is one of the methods that can be used by organizations to find out and assess how much employee satisfaction is with their work and their work environment. The reason for the assessment is to increase the level of job satisfaction of employees by giving recognition of their work (Hasibuan, 2016). Hasibuan (2016), says that many indicators affect the level of discipline of a person in an organization, one of which is remuneration or welfare salary which influences employee discipline because remuneration will give employees satisfaction and love for their workplace. If the employee's love for work is higher, the discipline will be better. Thus job satisfaction accompanied by work discipline will improve employee performance.

5.7. The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline

Thus, hypothesis 7 which states that Work Motivation has a positive effect through Work Discipline on employee performance at the Regional Secretariat of the General Section of East Luwu Regency, is accepted. According to Gomes (2016), performance is a function of work motivation and ability. Ability is inherent in a person and is innate and manifested in his actions at work, while work motivation is a very important aspect to drive one's creativity and ability to do a job, and always be enthusiastic in carrying out the work. Hasibuan (2016), says that among the goals of work motivation are creating a good working atmosphere and relationship, increasing a sense of responsibility for one's duties, and being able to increase one's discipline at work. Thus work motivation accompanied by work discipline will improve employee performance.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research data analysis and discussion that has been stated previously, it can be concluded, job

satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work discipline, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work discipline has a positive effect on employee performance, work has a positive effect on employee performance through work discipline, work motivation has a positive effect on employee performance through work discipline. good and high job satisfaction will have an impact on increasing work discipline. This can be indicated that with high and good job satisfaction each employee will be able to encourage employees to carry out their duties properly. Besides that, an employee's work motivation can have a real influence in improving the work discipline of other employees, so that employee motivation improves employee performance. Besides that, good job satisfaction and work motivation will affect employee performance. This indicates that good work discipline can improve employee performance in carrying out their duties. Based on the mediation test results show that Job Satisfaction can have an indirect effect on employee performance through Work Discipline. This indicates that good Job Satisfaction will provide high Work Discipline thereby encouraging employees to provide good work results. Likewise, well-managed work motivation will indirectly affect employee performance because well-managed work motivation will increase employee performance.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions stated above, there are several suggestions proposed for development and practical needs, especially at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency as follows: 1) The research results show that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, so that employees can improve Its performance through job satisfaction, what needs to be considered is that the leadership further increases the job satisfaction of its employees; 2) The results of the study show that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance so that leaders can improve their performance through work motivation. What needs to be considered is the work situation and cooperation between leaders and fellow employees, and 3) The research results show that Work Discipline has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance. To improve employee performance, it is necessary to improve work discipline.

REFERENCES

1. Anoraga, P., & Suyati, S. (2015). *Perilaku Keorganisasian*. PT. Pustaka Jaya.
2. Bavendam, J. (2000). How Do You Manage Turnover? in a Time of Lean Organizations and Dwindling Pools of Experienced Newhires. *Journal Special Report*, 3.
3. Bougie, R., & Sekaran, U. (2019). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach* (8th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
4. Cooper, D. R., & Emory, C. W. (2006). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis* (5th ed.). Erlangga.
5. Ghozali, I. (2021). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 26* (10th ed.). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
6. Gie, T. L. (2009). *Administrasi Perkantoran Modern*. Liberty.
7. Gomes, F. C. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Andi Offset.
8. Handoko, T. H. (2016). *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumberdaya Manusia*. BPFE Press.
9. Hasibuan, M. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bumi Aksara.
10. Huit, W. (2001). Motivation to Learn: An Overview. *Educational Psychology Interactive*, 12(3), 29–36.
11. Ibrahim, T. C. (2012). *Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai pada Inspektorat Kabupaten Aceh Utara*. Universitas Terbuka.
12. Ilahi, D. K., Mukzam, M. D., & Prasetya, A. (2017). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Disiplin Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasional. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 44(1), 31–39.
13. Keban, Y. T. (2007). Pembangunan Birokrasi di Indonesia: Agenda Kenegaraan yang Terabaikan. In *Pidato Pengukuran Guru Besar pada Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta*.
14. Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Perilaku Organisasi* (9th ed.). Salemba Empat.
15. Mangkunegara, A. A. A. P. (2016). *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia* (3rd ed.). Refika Aditama.
16. Markum, S. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. SMMAS.
17. Mas'ud, F. (2004). *Survei Diagnosis Organisasional (Konsep dan Aplikasi)*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
18. Mathis, R. L., Jackson, J. H., Valentine, S. R., & Meglich, P. (2019). *Human Resource Management* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.
19. Moekijat. (2010). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (Revisi). Mandar Maju.
20. Moenir, A. S. (1987). *Pendekatan Manusiawi dan Organisasi Terhadap Pembinaan Pegawai*. Gunung Agung.
21. Nathalia, D. (2016). *Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Perikanan dan Kelautan Provinsi Jawa Barat*. Universitas Widyatama.
22. Newstrom, J. W., & Davis, K. (2002). *Organizational*

“The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Work Discipline at the Regional Secretariat of East Luwu Regency, Indonesia”

- Behavior: Human Behavior at Work*. McGraw-Hill Companies Inc.
23. Nitisemito, A. S. (2018). *Manajemen Personalia (Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia)*. Ghalia Indonesia.
24. Noor, J. (2015). *Analisis Data Penelitian Ekonomi & Manajemen* (2nd ed.). Grasindo.
25. Pratama, R., & Nurbudiawati. (2016). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Disiplin Kerja Pegawai di Kelurahan Sukakarya Kecamatan Tarogong Kidul Kabupaten Garut. *Jurnal Pembangunan Dan Kebijakan Publik*, 7(2), 10–19.
26. Prawirosentono, S. (2014). *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia “Kebijakan Kinerja Karyawan”*: Kiat Membangun Organisasi Kompetitif Menjelang Perdagangan Bebas Dunia (5th ed.). BPFE.
27. Priyatno, D. (2008). *Mandiri Belajar SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Slution): Untuk Analisis Data dan Uji Statistik*. Mediakom.
28. Purwanto, N. (2007). Komunikasi Interpersonal dalam Keluarga. In *Laporan Lembaga Pengabdian Masyarakat*.
29. Ramadhani, D. S., & Dwihartanti, M. (2016). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Balai Pengembangan Kegiatan Belajar (BPKB) Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta (DIY). *Jurnal Pendidikan Administrasi Perkantoran-S1*, 5(2), 163–173.
30. Rivai, V., & Sagala, E. J. (2014). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan: Dari Teori Ke Praktik* (3rd ed.). Rajawali Pers.
31. Robbins, S. P., Judge, T. A., & Vohra, N. (2018). *Organizational Behavior* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
32. Santoso, S. (2020). *Panduan Lengkap SPSS 26*. PT Elex Media Komputindo.
33. Sastrohadiwiryo, S., & Hadaningsih Syuhada, A. (2019). *Manajemen Tenaga Kerja Indonesia: Pendekatan Administratif dan Operasional* (Revisi). Penerbit Sinar Baru.
34. Sedarmayanti. (2011). *Tata Kerja dan Produktivitas Kerja: Suatu Tinjauan dari Aspek Ergonomi atau Kaitan Antara Manusia dengan Lingkungan Kerjanya*. CV Mandar Maju.
35. Siagian, S. P. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (Satu). PT. Bumi Aksara.
36. Simamora, H. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (1st ed.). STIE YKPN.
37. Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. CV. Alfabeta.
38. Terry, G. R., & Rue, L. W. (2021). *Dasar-Dasar Manajemen* (Revisi). Bumi Aksara.
39. Uno, H. B. (2023). *Teori Motivasi dan Pengukurannya: Analisis di Bidang Pendidikan*. Bumi Aksara.
40. Usman, M. U. (2013). *Menjadi Guru Profesional*. Remaja Rosdakarya.
41. Wibowo. (2016). *Manajemen Kinerja* (5th ed.). Rajawali Pers.
42. Wursanto, I. (2009). *Dasar-Dasar Ilmu Organisasi* (2nd ed.). CV. Andi Offset.